

A DIFFERENT PERSPECTIVE ON THE STATUS MANAGEMENT FRAMEWORK

To cite this article: Collaborate, Current Science, Volume 5, No. 5-6, 2023, p. 16 – 26. - 0099-0001-2307-0202.

Our studies are in a format accredited, approved, and supported by EAALS - European Academic Studies and Laboratory Services. ("Scientific Studies - Current Science Georgia") "EAALS offers all our works, services, and publications to the world scientists at the stage of carrying our control, accreditation, and support processes to the international platform." ("CURRENT SCIENCE") ("Scientific Studies - Current Science Georgia")

ISSN: 2667-9515

Barcode: 977266795001

Editors Group:

Concessionaire: Tsisana Kharabadze

Niyaz Bokvadze

Prof. Sabrina Corbi

Prof. Samantha Lewes

Assoc. Prof. Osman Doruk

""• Current Science Multidisciplinary Academic Journal with Review Panel is a monthly multidisciplinary academic"" ("CURRENT SCIENCE A Different Look at Traffic Sociology and Driver ...") ("Scientific Studies - Current Science Georgia") ("Scientific Studies - Current Science Georgia")

journal with a multi-science peer-review." ("Scientific Studies - Current Science Georgia")

("Scientific Studies -

Current Science Georgia")

""The magazine will be at the subscriber's address in the first week of the month.""

("Scientific Studies - Current Science Georgia")

• The journal continues to be included in all international rankings and registrations. Quality articles and publications accelerate this ("Scientific Studies - Current Science Georgia")

""• Response or rejection time for applications varies between 30 and 90 days."" ("Scientific Studies - Current Science Georgia")

Author(s) Name Surname: Assoc.Prof. Kürşat Şahin
YILDIRIMER, Halil YILMAZ, PhD, Sinan ÇINKIR, PhD,

(Orcid.0000-0001-5896-2956) (Orcid.0009-0002-5242-8028)
(Orcid) 0000-0003-0652-4051)

University: St. Clements University Head of the Department of
Psychology) St. Clements University, Management Law, St.
Clements University, Management Law

Date :07.07.2023

Abstract

The status quo bias, which is one of the biggest problem people to change; there may be many reasons such as economic, sociological, psychological and rational reasons. the study firstly emphasized the psychological foundations on which status quo behavior is based, by explaining the connection between change and management. Afterwards, the relationship between the status quo and the administration was examined deeper, and the people that the status quoists put in front of change were mentioned. finally, by explaining what methods can be used to overcome the status quo - solution items for the status quo bias phenomenon are listed.

Limitedness

The limitations of the research are limited to the scope of the subject in the light of world literature and data. The research was limited to closely related author and literature topics. Restricted by literature review.

Notifications

Evaluation: Evaluated by internal and external consultants.

Conflict of Interest: The authors declared no conflict of interest regarding this article.

Financial Disclosure: The authors reported no use of financial support for this article.

Ethical Statement

Publication ethics of the relevant regulations of our university; It is a national-based scientific study that aims to ensure that scientific research and publications are carried out in

1

THIS JOURNAL INCLUDED IN MANY INDEXES, INCLUDING ADVANCED SCIENCES INDEX. ADVANCED SCIENCES INDEX (ASI) EUROPEAN SCIENCE EVALUATION CENTER WHERE TOGETHER KIRCHSTRASSE 4.56761 | RHINELAND-PALATINATE, GERMANY PHONE: +49(177) 8684-353 PHONE: +49(177) 8684-353 EMAILS:

ASI@EUROPE.DE

CURRENT SCIENCE

accordance with basic principles such as honesty, openness, objectivity, and respect for the findings and creations of others, and works for the realization of these principles in the field of related sciences.

ABSTRACT

The status quo bias, which is one of the most significant obstacles individuals have when attempting to make a change; there may be a variety of reasons for this, including economic, social, psychological, and rational reasons. The significance of the psychological foundations on which status quo behavior is based was initially emphasized by the study by providing an explanation of the connection between management and change. After that, a deeper look was taken at the connection between the status quo and the administration, and the individuals that the staunch defenders of the status quo cite as reasons to resist change were discussed. Finally, the status quo bias phenomenon is addressed by providing a list of potential solutions by elaborating on the different approaches that can be taken to challenge the status quo.

Keywords: *Status quo, Status quo bias, Management, Management Law*

1. INTRODUCTION

One of the ideas that the 20th and 21st centuries brought with them was that of change, which in reality goes all the way back to ancient times. Every industry has been impacted by the age of change, which has manifested itself in its own unique way. Despite this, there are still many people who are resistant to change for a variety of reasons, including apprehension about the future, a desire to maintain their current level of comfort, and the fear of the unknown. The continued existence of the current situation is undeniably the most significant of these roadblocks. individuals' unwillingness to give up items or acts in the scenario they are in may

2

THIS JOURNAL INCLUDED IN MANY INDEXES, INCLUDING ADVANCED SCIENCES INDEX. ADVANCED SCIENCES INDEX (ASI) EUROPEAN SCIENCE EVALUATION CENTER WHERE TOGETHER KIRCHSTRASSE 4.56761 | RHINELAND-PALATINATE, GERMANY PHONE: +49(177) 8684-353 PHONE: +49(177) 8684-353 EMAILS: ASI@EUROPE.DE

CURRENT SCIENCE

be described psychologically as a result of status quo behavior. However, this conduct also suggests that individuals attach greater importance to the present situation and order that they are in.

When seen through the lens of Türkiye, the issue of change reveals itself to be irrelevant to the current state of affairs. Some of the studies emphasize the existence of a status quo in the change that took place in and after 1923 and that it is an obstacle in front of Turkey, which is tried to be established after 1923 (Aktan and Yay,2016; 50). On the other hand, some of the studies suggest that Turkish Foreign Policy, which developed within the framework of westernism and status quos after the independence struggle, emphasizes that it is an obstacle to change (Bolukbaş, 2021; 86).

status quo prejudice; It is obvious that it should be investigated not only from a behavioral and psychological standpoint, but also from a managerial and administrative point of view. Due to the fact that management is the oldest of the arts (Ertekin, 2004; 55), as well as the fact that it is simultaneously emerging as a branch of law, it is beneficial to examine the status quo bias on the basis of administrative law.

The structure, powers, and obligations of the state as well as other public organizations and public services are regulated by administrative law, which is a subfield of administrative law. Because it has a status quo within this formation, administrative law, which consists of rules and principles that regulate public administration and services, might not be subject to change. Administrative law regulates public administration and services. When it comes to making any changes to the legislation that governs the country, there is a standstill since the status quo is often backed by influential interest groups.

Following the presentation of a conceptual framework, definitions of the status quo and status quoism, and an examination of the link between the status quo and management, the study focuses first on bringing to light how the status quo is understood in the existing body of academic research. In the end, it provides solutions as a response to the behavior that has been maintained as the status quo within the administration.

2. CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

CURRENT SCIENCE

The phrase "to maintain the status quo" is derived from the Latin phrase "status quo," which, in common usage, means to resist or oppose change. The meaning of the phrase "status quo" as defined by the Turkish Language Association (TDK) is "the situation of the preservation of the ongoing order, the enduring situation." "The condition that should be or continue according to the treaties that are currently in force, the permanent condition." is defined as "the permanent condition." According to the findings of the study, maintaining the status quo is the antithesis of embracing change when seen in this light. (Aktan and Yay; 2016; 51).

The phrase "people who want to maintain the status quo openly or implicitly and are closed to change" is one possible definition of the term "status quo." According to Sezer and Sar's research (2017; 200), the perspective of status quo in management can be defined as the fact that superiors and subordinates continue their time-honored routines and are not open to incorporating innovation into their day-to-day activities. Another study found that confidentiality and secrecy are the status quo in the administration. This situation renders the citizens defenseless and powerless against the bureaucracy by concealing the corruption that exists within the institutions (Çoban, 1999; 177). When it comes to the evaluation of the status quo in the administration based on the courts, he states that, as an example, the process of preparing minutes in the courts frequently prevents the provision of justice, and that justice is lost among the archives of the courthouse (Sezer and Sar, 2017; 201). This information is found in Sezer and Sar's study (2017; 201).

3. STATUS AND MANAGEMENT

One of the most significant impediments to change is the status quo, and for those who uphold the status quo, maintaining their interests in the status quo rather than adapting to change is a much higher priority than the new opportunities that change presents. It is imperative for nations that do not want to wither and die in this age of change to triumph over the status quo. According to this point of view, in order for Turkey to survive in this age of change, it is necessary for the country to undergo change. In order for this to occur, the status quo, which tends to slow down both the administration and the administration by placing it in a vicious loop, must be destroyed. This is necessary because the existing quo tends to slow

CURRENT SCIENCE

down both the administration and the administration. Because the status quo is seriously effective in Turkey. In order to get rid of the status quo, the first thing that is required is a belief in change, and then a certain amount of work must be taken in order to keep that conviction alive. If this happens, Turkey, free from the status quo and the status quo, will be a country where mistakes are replaced by truth, old ones are replaced by new ones, interests are replaced by virtue and good morals. In order for Türkiye to stay up with the times and overcome these challenges, it is necessary. But how exactly will this take place? How exactly do you plan to overturn the current situation in Turkey? How will Turkey get past the many challenges that stand in the way of change? It is required to do an analysis of the many players that make up the status quo in Turkey in order to provide answers to these problems. The political elites that constitute the status quo political power center in Turkey and the bureaucrats that implement the decisions taken by them, the interest and pressure groups that directly or indirectly affect the decision-making processes, the monetary power center formed by the big rich; that is, the bourgeoisie consists of the media, which has the power to influence communication and public opinion, and most importantly, the army, which holds the most important positions of power in the country.

The political elite is the class that has the most influence in this country. According to Evmez (2020; 53), the capacity of the elite to influence the political ideas of the general population is the source of their power. Because elites are able to guide the political views of the people, they have the capacity to impose any form of status quo that serves their own interests on the masses. In this context, elites may be a significant barrier to change (Duzgun, 1998; 329). It's possible that the problem has something to do with materiality for the bureaucratic group that puts the choices made by the elite into action. According to Dursun (1992), page 133, the term "bureaucracy" literally means "rooms where state affairs are carried out," and it is responsible for putting into action the choices that are made by the government. In addition to using state resources, bureaucrats tend to earn advantages over other groups by their use of these resources. Therefore, they engage in the administrative system in accordance with their own interests, with the purpose of financial gain and granting them greater rights than other groups. The interests of the bureaucracy, as can be seen, both maintain the status quo and prevent change (Aktaş and Yay, 2016; 54).

CURRENT SCIENCE

There is a group known as the bureaucracy, as well as interest groups and pressure groups, which all have an impact on decision making. On the other hand, interest and pressure groups are movements that can be used by more than one person together, freedom of collective action, that build their groups from temporary or permanent people, and that seek goals that individuals cannot accomplish alone (Eray, 2019; 238). Interest and pressure groups are movements that can be used by more than one person together, freedom of collective action. In the procedures by which choices are made, interest and pressure groups; Groups such as professional chambers and labor unions are able to apply pressure on and influence political decisions in Turkey so that they are in accordance with particular interests. At the same time, the group known as the bourgeoisie, which has the financial power in their hands, is also influential on the choices that are made on the basis of administration and administration. The group known as the bourgeoisie, which is able to put a barrier in the way of progress due to the material wealth it possesses, can at times be a supporter of the status quo, despite the fact that it shifts according to the interests it prioritizes. On the other hand, the media side has played an effective part in Turkish political history due to its ability to influence and control public opinion (Temir, 2021; 155). This ability has allowed it to play such a role. According to Aktan and Yay (2016; 55), the army is the most significant group responsible for maintaining the status quo. They also claimed that the interventions of the military in political life where the reason Turkey was unable to keep up with the times of change.

4. THE RESISTANCE BROUGHT TOGETHER WITH THE STATUS

Alteration is accompanied by a wide variety of dynamics. What should be done; this not only gets rid of the uncertainty that cropped up as a result of the presence of change, but it also lessens the intensity of the resistance that was caused by the uncertainty. When it comes to diminishing the opposition of a collective group unified around the status quo and the administrative law, various steps may be adopted in order not to make the citizen susceptible to bureaucracy. resistance is said to be essential; it is essential to take measures as it tends to ignore the demands of change and new needs of the society. A resistance to change (Tuncer, 2013; 392–393); - From an economic point of view, financial concerns and uncertainty about working conditions. Even though one particular group within the organization is responsible

6

CURRENT SCIENCE

for the management of the institution's financial resources, the impending change that will strip them of this legal status may cause a significant conflict of interest between the group and the institution.

From a sociological point of view, resistance to change may emerge whenever an existing social value is threatened by an impending change.

In terms of human psychology, the fact that long-term habits won't be formed after a certain amount of time can be a source of insecurity due to the fact that this fact is viewed from a psychological point of view. Because of this, there is pushback against change.

From a logical point of view, if the individual perceives that the change will cost them more than it will benefit them, they have a basis for developing a rational opposition to the change.

The following methods are recommended by Tuncer (2013; 397-398) in order to ensure justice in legal processes and to prevent resistance to change displayed by the status quo in the name of the welfare of the citizen: Communication and Education, Participation and Support, Bargaining and Concession, Threat and Coercion, Manipulation and Cooptation, Planning for Change and Experimental Practice, forecasting method, and Economic Incentive Measures are the ten pillars of the change management framework.

Table.1 Methods to Prevent Change Resistance Activity

<p>1. Communication and Education</p>	<p>The method of communication and training is linked to the openness of the communication channel between superiors and subordinates, and when mutual trust is concerned, resistance to change is expected to decrease.</p> <p>In the education wing, on the other hand, the resistance of individuals with improved knowledge and skills to change decreases. The knowledge base, which eliminates uncertainty, contributes to the reduction of resistance.</p>
<p>2. Participation and Support</p>	<p>In the part of participation and support, it was predicted that the resistance of the status quoists who participated in the planning and implementation of change decreased.</p> <p>The supporting phase occurs when superiors support subordinates to improve themselves. This support prevents the status quo by giving certain trainings to a certain extent.</p>
<p>3. Bargaining and Compromise</p>	<p>At the stage of bargaining and making concessions, trying to find a middle way through negotiation by opening the bargaining wing over the status quo, for example, between subordinates and superiors, brings with it the situation of concession. This is how the aggression brought about by the status quo can be prevented.</p>
<p>4. Threat and Pressure</p>	<p>Although threats and pressure seem to be more dominant as a method, they actually contain perspectives that can be considered dangerous in terms of management and administration. This method is called as a method that should be put into effect when there is no application of another method in the studies.</p>

5. Manipulation and Cooptation	<p>Any action to be taken by making things perceived differently by showing them as different from what they are will reduce the resistance.</p> <p>Cooptation, on the other hand, means making those who are against a subject a part of the problems and solutions related to that subject. In this way, people or groups that show resistance will seek a solution by feeling themselves in the problem instead of just being on the wing of criticism against the situation or event. This shows that even if the resistance is not completely destroyed, it is broken to a certain extent.</p>
6. Planning for Change and Experimental Implementation	<p>In order for a change not to meet with resistance, it is necessary to put it forward at the right time and plan every step of it. As many uncertainties disappear at this stage, resistance will be broken.</p> <p>The trial wing, on the other hand, is actually a good indicator for anyone who is a party to change, in order not to suffer irreversible losses. If the desired results are obtained after the trial application, the resistance will be broken to a large extent.</p>
7. Estimation Method	<p>The prediction in question; It is related to identifying areas of resistance and reasons for resistance. If the areas of resistance and their causes are identified, it is very important to detect these phenomena, as it will be easier to eliminate or reduce the strength of the resistance.</p>
8. Economic Incentives and Measures	<p>Since most of the resistance actions are related to economic reasons, economic incentives and measures should be used to minimize resistance. The fact that people or groups who have not experienced economic loss have a more positive view of change is an indicator of decreased resistance.</p>

Source: Tuncer, 2013; 398 -399

CONCLUSION

The shift, which has been occurring from the earliest known times, has made its presence known in a great many spheres and has taken up a significant amount of space in the 21st century. One of the fields that is being affected by change, management and administration, wanted to develop and change, but it ran into a change rebellion called "status quo" in the literature due to the skepticism that exists in the creation of humanity. The status quo bias, which is one of the most significant barriers to change; There might be a variety of reasons for this, including social, economic, psychological, and rational grounds.

The importance of the psychological underpinnings on which status quo behavior is founded was first stressed by the research by providing an explanation of the link between management and change. When the conduct of the status quo is investigated on the basis of administrative law, it is discovered that the existing quo is often maintained by strong parties. This is because administrative law favors the status quo. After that, a conceptual framework is drawn, and it is emphasized that the status quo, which is examined on the basis of confidentiality and administration, makes the citizens of the country susceptible to bureaucracy, and it prevents the provision of justice. This is done by pointing out that the status quo is examined on the basis of confidentiality and administration. After then, a more in-depth examination of the link between the status quo and the administration was conducted, and the hurdles that the status quoists set in front of change were brought up and discussed. The research takes into account Turkey's viewpoint of the status quo, and it identifies the individuals responsible for maintaining the status quo in Turkey as well as the reasons for maintaining it. In this context, the political elites, bureaucracy, bourgeoisie, media, and army were all taken into account, and it was shown which factors each of these groups had in their hands when it came to leaning for the status quo. In this context, the research focused on the resistance of groups that are or may be in favor of maintaining the status quo. Initially, the researchers touched on the factors that contribute to this resistance, and then they enumerated the strategies and procedures that can reduce or eliminate this resistance.

In this regard, despite the fact that human beings are predisposed to adhere to the status quo due to their natural tendency to have their doubts misconstrued as skepticism and their

reluctance to go outside of their comfort zones, this predisposition may be overcome by following certain courses of action and strategies.

RESOURCES

- Aktan, CC, & Yay, S. (2016). Status quo and resistance to change in Turkey. *Journal of Organization and Management Sciences*, 8 (1), 49-71.
- BOLUKBAŞI, YZ (2021). CONTINUITY AND CHANGE IN TURKISH FOREIGN POLICY: KEMALIZM AND CHP. *Academic Sensitivities*, 8 (15), 83-110.
- Shepherd, O. (1999). Bribery as a type of political corruption and its economic effects. *Atatürk University Journal of Economics and Administrative Sciences*, 13 (1).
- Dursun, D. (1992). Bureaucracy theory and management. Of *Journal of Social policy Conferences* (No. 37-38, pp. 133-149).
- DUZGÜN, A. (1998). Terms of Change and Social Change. *Journal of Ankara University Faculty of Theology*, 38 (1-4), 309-332.
- Ertekin, Y. (2004). Contemporary management and control. *Car University Journal of Social Sciences*, 1 (1), 55-67.
- Eray, ACAR (2019). Functions and methods of pressure groups in participatory democracies. *Dumlupınar University Journal of Social Sciences*, (61), 235-249.
- EVMEZ, Z. (2020). THE EFFECT OF THE POLITICAL ELITE RECONCILIATION ON THE PEOPLE'S ATTITUDE TO THE EU IN TURKEY. *Journal of Eurasian Social and Economic Studies*, 7 (1), 51-73.
- Ozbudun, E. (2007). The judicial activism of the Turkish constitutional court and the reaction of the political elite. *Ankara University Journal of SBF*, 62 (03), 257-268.

CURRENT SCIENCE

SEZER, Ö., & SARI, C. (2017). THE EFFECTS OF THE NEW PUBLIC ADMINISTRATION APPROACH TO THE TURKISH JUDICIAL SYSTEM. *Journal of Mehmet Akif Ersoy University Social Science Institute*, 9 (20).

Tuncer, P. (2013). Resistance to change in the change management process. *Nineteen May University Journal of Education Faculty*, 32 (1).

Temir, E. (2021). Media in Turkic Republics. *F. Yıldız*, 30, 155-182.